

Assessing Expectancy Bias in Listener Evaluations of AI and Human Music Compositions

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Abstract

Recent advancements in AI-driven music composition have ignited debates over the creative quality and emotional impact of computer-generated versus human-composed works. In this study, we explore these dimensions by evaluating a range of songs — each derived from distinct creative prompts varying in style, instrumentation, and tempo — that were produced via two methods: AI generation using Suno AI and human composition by a professional music producer. Participants in an online listening experiment rated these pieces on creativity, authenticity and induced emotions. The experimental design employed a between-subjects approach: one group of participants was kept unaware that any songs were generated by AI, while the other group was informed that both AI- and human-produced pieces would be evaluated, though neither group knew the exact number or identity of the AI-generated works. This covert versus overt information manipulation was implemented to critically assess potential expectancy and bias effects in listener evaluations. Therefore, the objective of the study was to provide new insights into the subtle perceptual boundaries between AI and human creative processes in music, highlighting both the strengths and limitations of current generative models in creating emotionally and artistically compelling compositions. Initial results revealed that, irrespective of the participants' expectation, on average AI-generated songs received lower ratings than non-AI-generated compositions across all measured criteria. Notably, while both groups rated AI pieces lower, the group informed about the presence of AI-generated music exhibited more pronounced differences between the two categories. This suggests that explicitly informing listeners about the involvement of AI in the composition process may modulate their evaluations by amplifying negative expectancy biases against AI-generated music.

1 Introduction

A growing body of research has investigated listener judgments of AI-generated versus human-composed music along the dimensions of creativity, authenticity, and emotionality. Generally,

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listeners exhibit skepticism toward AI’s creative and emotional capacities. For example, White et al. (2025) showed that the same musical excerpt is rated as significantly less expressive and emotionally moving when participants believe it to be AI-composed, even though overall enjoyment remains unchanged. When asked to guess the source, participants attributed greater emotional depth to passages they thought were human-created, demonstrating a bias driven by perceived authorship.

Similarly, Bellaïche et al. (2023) demonstrated a general preference for human-created artwork over AI-created artwork, partly because people ascribe greater emotional meaning and depth to human creations. In the musical domain, Hong et al. (2022) manipulated whether an AI music system was described as having high versus low “human-like” traits and as being independently creative. They found that anthropomorphizing the AI increased its acceptance “as a musician,” but informing listeners of the AI’s autonomous creativity did not significantly alter their evaluations of its music (Hong et al., 2022).

Beyond these attribution effects, several studies directly compare AI and human outputs on objective quality measures. In a melody-continuation paradigm, Schreiber et al. (2024) evaluated ChatGPT- and Magenta-generated melodies against music student-composed continuations and found that the AI pieces scored lower in aesthetic quality. Likewise, Frieler and Zaddach (2022) reported that listeners preferred human-performed jazz solos to algorithmically generated ones, despite correctly identifying the source only about 64.6% of the time.

In the context of genre-specific production, Sarmiento et al. (2024) observed that although participants often could not reliably distinguish AI from human progressive rock/metal compositions, they nonetheless favored the human works for their narrative cohesion, creative flair, and emotional satisfaction. Conversely, Liao (2024) demonstrated that an RNN-based piano composition system achieved listener ratings on par with human performances in creativity, expressiveness, and aesthetic appeal—indicating that with advanced modeling and careful selection, AI music can approach human levels.

Furthermore, socio-cultural context plays a crucial role in creative bias evaluations, suggesting that listener backgrounds may interact with AI authorship perceptions. Considering the importance of these contextual factors, Déguernel and Sturm (2023) recommend implementing methodological safeguards in future studies to more effectively account for and mitigate bias when evaluating computational creative outputs.

Taken together, the existing research suggests a tendency for AI-generated music to be rated somewhat lower in perceived creativity, authenticity, and emotional impact compared to human-composed works. As generative models advance, listeners’ beliefs about authorship may play an even more significant role in shaping these evaluations.

Accordingly, our study has two principal aims: (1) to evaluate the latest state-of-the-art AI music-generation models using up-to-date techniques, and (2) to examine how listeners’ assumptions about a piece’s origin (human vs. AI) shape their evaluations, since perceived authorship bias may intensify as AI quality advances. We therefore assess the established dimensions of authenticity, creativity, and induced emotion, drawing on the frameworks and measures discussed above.

2 Methods

2.1 Measures and item construction

2.1.1 Authenticity items

Authenticity in music is a multifaceted construct that has been discussed in diverse contexts for decades. For example, Auslander (1998) examines live performance and authenticity in rock culture, Armstrong (2004) analyzes the construction of authenticity in pop music, Edidin (1998) distinguishes between historical and personal authenticity in classical performance, and Frith (2004) explores its aesthetic and social functions. Kivy (1995) synthesizes these perspectives as the “quintessence of authenticity,” highlighting the tension between fidelity to the work and artistic originality. More recently, scholars have begun to investigate how these traditional notions apply to AI-generated music (Tan, 2024; Günay, 2025).

For authenticity, our approach builds directly on the psychological dimensions of cultural versus personal authenticity outlined by Wu et al. (2017). To operationalize perceived authenticity, we used the following items, all presented on 5-point Likert-type scales (1 = strongly disagree; 5 = strongly agree):

- “The music feels real and sincere.”
- “The music sounds honest and not artificial or forced.”
- “The music sounds authentic and unadulterated.”
- “The music conveys the impression that it was created with genuine passion and dedication.”

2.1.2 Musical creativity items

Musical creativity has been explored across a wide range of disciplines—including psychology, neuroscience, cultural studies, education, and therapy. A recent bibliometric analysis by Yujia et al. (2024) offers a comprehensive synthesis of this multifaceted literature. In parallel, computational approaches to music creativity emerged in the 1990s, from rule-based algorithmic composition (Papadopoulos and Wiggins, 1999) and heuristic search techniques (Wiggins, 2006) to fitness-based evaluation (Carnovalini and Rodà, 2020; Herremans et al., 2017) and operationalization frameworks (Bodily and Ventura, 2024). More recently, the advent of deep generative AI has reignited interest in algorithmic creativity, as demonstrated by systems such as OpenAI’s Jukebox (Dhariwal et al., 2020), Google’s MusicLM (Agostinelli et al., 2023), Meta’s MusicGen (Copet et al., 2023), Riffusion (Riffusion, 2023), Suno AI (Suno AI, 2023), or Seed-Music (Bai et al., 2024).

Musical creativity is often conceptualized along two core dimensions: novelty and value (Schiavio et al., 2022). Novelty refers to the introduction of original, imaginative ideas that extend beyond familiar conventions, while value denotes the artistic significance and contextual appropriateness of those ideas. A composition that merely surprises with unconventional elements—such as unexpected harmonic progressions or improvisational turns—does not guarantee a creative experience unless it also demonstrates craftsmanship and coherence (Schiavio et al., 2022). In addition, computational creativity research highlights surprise—defined as the degree to which a work defies listener expectations—as a key driver of perceived creativity (Grace and Maher, 2014).

To capture these facets in our study, we employ four self-constructed items:

- “The music sounds original and imaginative.”
- “The music gives the impression of creativity and artistry.”
- “The music surprises with unexpected or unusual elements.”
- “The music sounds unique and stands out from other music.”

2.1.3 Induced emotions

Induced emotional responses represent a vital complement to authenticity and creativity in music perception. Indeed, many studies comparing AI-generated and human-composed works underscore emotional engagement as a key driver of listener judgments. In our study, we quantified emotional induction using the Geneva Emotional Music Scale (GEMS-9) by Zentner et al. (2008), which assesses nine distinct emotion categories. Because our primary aim was to capture the overall strength of emotional engagement rather than individual emotion profiles, we computed a single composite score by averaging across all GEMS-9 subscales. Consequently, higher composite values indicate music that elicits a broader and more intense emotional response. This approach is consistent with previous studies that prioritize aggregate affective intensity when investigating general arousal or engagement in musical settings (Abdou et al., 2024).

2.1.4 Summary

In summary, our objective was to capture participants’ overarching evaluations of authenticity, creativity, and induced emotions without overly fragmenting the constructs. Although each item within a scale pinpoints a particular facet, prior literature suggests that both authenticity and creativity in music are multifaceted concepts (e.g., historical vs. personal authenticity, originality vs. novelty). By incorporating four items per scale and allowing them to converge into a single dimension, we

preserved nuance while ensuring reliable measurement of overall perceptions. Similarly, we relied on GEMS-9 in an aggregated manner to gauge the strength of emotional induction, irrespective of specific emotions.

We averaged the items for authenticity, creativity, and induced emotions into three composite variables, which served as outcome measures in subsequent Linear Mixed Models (LMMs). Consequently, each composite score ranges from 1 to 5, where higher values indicate stronger perceived authenticity, creativity, or emotional induction. Each LMM included random intercepts for participants (to account for individual-level variability) and fixed effects for the main experimental manipulations. This modeling strategy aligns with our goal of examining how different musical conditions (e.g., AI vs. human-composed) influence overall judgments of authenticity, creativity, and emotional induction in the informed and uninformed condition.

2.2 Music generation

Many commercially available AI music agents provide only rudimentary controls, making it challenging to systematically manipulate musical parameters across conditions. Conversely, research-oriented models that offer fine-grained controllability often fall short in naturalness and production quality compared to their commercial counterparts. To strike a balance between experimental rigor and audio fidelity, we selected Suno AI v4.0 (Suno AI, 2023), a commercial platform benchmarked for state-of-the-art realism in AI-generated music (Grötschla et al., 2025). This choice ensures both high production quality and the ability to assess the impact of cutting-edge generative technology in authentic, real-world scenarios.

The pieces of music for the human-generated category were composed and produced by a professional music producer and singer-songwriter. The specifications (prompts) for the four pieces were identical for the human producer and for Suno AI, ensuring a consistent range of genre/style, instrumentation, tempo, etc.:

- Song 1: Write a funky groove song at 95 bpm with a prominent bass line and tight drums. The lyrics should reflect a summery vibe. Focus on rhythm and groove with catchy vocal hooks and a danceable character.
- Song 2: Create a bouncy, danceable track with soulful vocals and an overall uplifting, empowering tone. It should inspire hope and capture the essence of resilience in today's world.
- Song 3: Evoke the feeling of a walk in nature. Use acoustic instruments to create an organic, earthy vibe. Lyrics should be about discovering your true passion in life and the courage to pursue it (130-150 bpm).
- Song 4: Compose a song featuring at least one electronic element in the instrumentation, with the rest chosen freely. Melodies should be memorable and catchy. Lyrics about love and relationships (110-120 bpm).

Note that for each prompt we generated two distinct versions (one by Suno AI, one by the human producer), which we refer to collectively as “Song 1” through “Song 4” for simplicity. Each numbered song thus represents a pair of versions based on the same creative prompt. All excerpts were trimmed to 30 seconds each to ensure uniform listening duration and to focus evaluations on a comparable structural segment. We chose not to present full songs in order to minimize dropout and maintain consistent attention across trials.

In order to maximize acoustic comparability and prevent listeners from using vocal artifacts as a cue to AI generation, we had the same professional singer re-record all lead vocals—including those originally produced by Suno AI—without altering melody or rhythm and with careful timbre matching. By holding the singer's voice constant, we ensured that any detection of “AI” or “human” origin would depend on emotional and structural cues rather than on obvious voice quality differences.

2.3 Participants

Thirty-two individuals participated in the study; one was excluded due to technical issues, yielding a final sample of 31 (12 male, 19 female; age: $M = 42.71$, $SD = 17.10$). Participants were randomly assigned to the Uninformed Group (UG; $n = 16$) or the Informed Group (IG; $n = 15$). The UG

was told that the study examined the perception of emotions, creativity, and authenticity in music. The IG received the same instructions plus the information that each excerpt they heard would be either AI-generated or human-composed, without specifying how many of each. They got the information only once at the outset. On average, participants scored 68.1 on the Goldsmiths Musical Sophistication Index (Müllensiefen et al., 2014).

Although group sizes differed slightly and a few participants did not rate every song, this does not compromise our analyses: all linear mixed-effects models included participant-level random intercepts and converged successfully, ensuring robust estimation under unbalanced and partially missing data conditions. All participants provided informed consent electronically before beginning the study and were free to withdraw at any time without penalty. The study was conducted in accordance with the World Medical Association's Declaration of Helsinki (2013).

2.4 Procedure

The experiment was administered online via the SoSciSurvey platform (Leiner, 2025). Upon logging in, participants first provided demographic details and completed the general-factor questionnaire of the Goldsmiths Musical Sophistication Index (Müllensiefen et al., 2014). They were then randomly assigned to the Uninformed Group (UG) or the Informed Group (IG), receiving only a one-time briefing at the outset. Next, each participant listened to eight excerpts (four human-composed, four AI-generated) in a fully counterbalanced sequence. After each excerpt, participants rated its authenticity, creativity, and the emotions it induced using 5-point Likert scales.

3 Results

Mixed linear models were fitted to predict participants' ratings on authenticity, induced emotions, and creativity. In all models, the fixed effects included the source of the music (human vs. AI), the individual questionnaire item (treated as a categorical variable), and their interaction. Participants were included as a random effect (VP) to account for inter-individual variability. Below, Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) for authenticity, induced emotions (emotionality), and creativity ratings for each song by group and by source. In addition, Table 2 presents the results of the pairwise comparisons between AI and human ratings. For each song and for both UG and IG, Cohen's d values and the corresponding p -values (derived from Welch's t -tests) are reported. We used Welch's t -test for these comparisons because it is robust to unequal variances and unbalanced sample sizes between conditions. Although multiple pairwise tests were conducted, we report unadjusted p -values alongside effect sizes, interpreting significance in the context of the overall pattern of results.

3.1 Authenticity ratings

For authenticity ratings, the model in Song 2 yielded an estimated intercept of 2.64 (SE = 0.21) and a significant positive effect for human-composed music, with an estimated coefficient of 1.26 (SE = 0.21, $z = 6.01$, $p < 0.001$). In addition, item-specific effects contributed further variability (e.g., one effect was estimated at -0.57 , SE = 0.21, $z = -2.70$, $p = 0.007$). To further examine the difference between AI-generated and human-composed music, independent (Welch's) t -tests were conducted for the Uninformed Group (UG) and the Informed Group (IG). In Song 1, UG showed a Cohen's d of 0.43 ($p = 0.024$) while IG showed a Cohen's d of -0.33 ($p = 0.084$). In Song 2, the UG and IG displayed larger effect sizes (Cohen's $d = 0.87$, $p < 0.001$ and 1.42 , $p < 0.001$, respectively). In Song 3, differences were minimal for the UG (Cohen's $d = 0.02$, $p = 0.911$) but reached significance in the IG (Cohen's $d = -0.69$, $p < 0.001$). Finally, in Song 4 both groups showed robust differences, with UG reporting a Cohen's d of 0.71 ($p < 0.001$) and IG a Cohen's d of 0.71 ($p < 0.001$). Model quality indices for Song 2, for example, included a log-likelihood of -308.22 , a scale parameter of 0.63, and a group-level (participant) variance of 0.65 (SE = 0.26), indicating acceptable residual variance. Overall, these findings suggest that authenticity ratings robustly favor human-composed music, with some variability between UG and IG. Figure 1 illustrates the mean authenticity ratings (\pm 95% CI) for Songs 1–4 in both the Uninformed Group (UG) and the Informed Group (IG).

Table 1: Descriptive statistics across three rating dimensions (Authenticity, Emotionality, and Creativity) by Song, Group (UG = Uninformed Group, IG = Informed Group), and Source.

Song	Group	Source	Authenticity		Emotionality		Creativity	
			Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Song 1	UG	AI	3.107	1.317	2.095	1.155	3.018	1.272
	UG	Human	3.625	1.071	2.183	1.162	2.857	1.103
	IG	AI	3.696	1.143	2.341	1.392	3.179	1.282
	IG	Human	3.357	0.903	2.103	1.065	2.768	1.221
Song 2	UG	AI	2.482	1.293	1.873	1.043	2.089	1.180
	UG	Human	3.609	1.292	2.181	1.175	2.766	1.306
	IG	AI	2.286	1.022	1.675	0.875	2.071	1.076
	IG	Human	3.679	0.936	2.214	1.107	2.929	1.142
Song 3	UG	AI	4.071	0.806	2.286	1.050	2.964	1.078
	UG	Human	4.089	0.880	2.341	1.234	2.875	1.308
	IG	AI	4.446	0.784	2.643	1.329	3.286	1.155
	IG	Human	3.867	0.892	2.481	1.177	3.267	0.936
Song 4	UG	AI	3.179	1.295	2.040	1.091	2.393	1.186
	UG	Human	3.950	0.852	2.481	1.295	2.533	1.295
	IG	AI	3.250	1.164	2.119	1.157	2.571	1.189
	IG	Human	3.964	0.808	2.524	1.282	3.000	1.236

Table 2: Pairwise comparisons (AI vs. human): Cohen’s d and p -values by Song and Group across rating dimensions.

Song	Group	Authenticity		Emotionality		Creativity	
		d	p	d	p	d	p
Song 1	UG	0.431	0.024	0.075	0.550	-0.135	0.476
	IG	-0.329	0.084	-0.192	0.129	-0.328	0.085
Song 2	UG	0.872	<0.001	0.276	0.023	0.542	0.004
	IG	1.421	<0.001	0.541	<0.001	0.772	<0.001
Song 3	UG	0.021	0.911	0.048	0.701	-0.074	0.694
	IG	-0.689	<0.001	-0.129	0.301	-0.018	0.923
Song 4	UG	0.709	<0.001	0.367	0.003	0.113	0.543
	IG	0.713	<0.001	0.332	0.009	0.353	0.064

3.2 Induced emotions

For induced emotions, the model in Song 1 yielded an intercept of 2.93 (SE = 0.19, $p < 0.001$). However, the effect for human-composed music was not significant (-0.25 , SE = 0.23, $z = -1.07$, $p = 0.283$); item-level effects were more pronounced (e.g., one effect was -1.50 , SE = 0.23, $z = -6.44$, $p < 0.001$). This model was based on 504 observations from 28 groups with a log-likelihood of -675.27 , a scale parameter of 0.76, and a group-level variance of 0.30 (SE = 0.11). Pairwise comparisons revealed that in Song 1 the UG had a negligible effect (Cohen’s $d = 0.08$, $p = 0.55$) and the IG a slightly negative effect (Cohen’s $d = -0.19$, $p = 0.13$). For Song 2, the UG showed a moderate effect (Cohen’s $d = 0.28$, $p = 0.023$) and the IG a stronger effect (Cohen’s $d = 0.54$, $p < 0.001$). For Song 3, the Uninformed Group (UG) exhibited virtually no source effect on emotional induction (Cohen’s $d = 0.048$, $p = 0.701$), indicating that AI- and human-composed excerpts elicited comparable emotional responses. Likewise, the Informed Group (IG) showed a negligible difference (Cohen’s $d = -0.129$, $p = 0.301$), suggesting that even when participants knew about the origin, their emotional ratings remained effectively unchanged. In Song 4 both UG (Cohen’s $d = 0.37$, $p = 0.003$) and IG (Cohen’s $d = 0.33$, $p = 0.009$) exhibited moderate effects. Overall, emotionality ratings were modestly affected by the source, suggesting that both AI-generated

Figure 1: Mean authenticity ratings (\pm 95% CI) for songs S1–S4, displayed separately for the Uninformed Group (UG) and Informed Group (IG). Within each group, human-composed sources are shown in lighter color shades, and AI-generated sources in darker shades.

Figure 2: Mean induced emotions ratings (\pm 95% CI) for songs S1–S4, displayed separately for the Uninformed Group (UG) and Informed Group (IG). Within each group, human-composed sources are shown in lighter color shades, and AI-generated sources in darker shades.

and human-composed music evoke relatively similar emotional responses. Figure 2 displays the mean induced emotions ratings (\pm 95% CI) for Songs 1–4, demonstrating the relatively modest and variable differences between AI- and human-composed excerpts in both groups.

3.3 Creativity ratings

For creativity, the model in Song 2 estimated an intercept of 2.05 (SE = 0.22, $p < 0.001$) and a robust effect for human-composed music (1.09, SE = 0.23, $z = 4.74$, $p < 0.001$). Independent t-tests showed that in Song 1 the UG produced a small negative effect (Cohen’s $d = -0.14$, $p = 0.48$) and the IG a somewhat larger negative effect (Cohen’s $d = -0.33$, $p = 0.085$). In Song 2, the UG and IG had moderate positive effects (Cohen’s $d = 0.54$, $p = 0.004$ and 0.77 , $p < 0.001$, respectively). In Song 3, the UG reported a negligible effect (Cohen’s $d = -0.07$, $p = 0.694$), while in Song 4

Figure 3: Mean creativity ratings (\pm 95% CI) for songs S1–S4, displayed separately for the Uninformed Group (UG) and Informed Group (IG). Within each group, human-composed sources are shown in lighter color shades, and AI-generated sources in darker shades.

the UG and IG showed positive effects of 0.11 ($p = 0.54$) and 0.35 ($p = 0.064$), respectively. For instance, the creativity model for Song 2 was based on 232 observations from 30 participants, with a log-likelihood of -326.06 , a scale parameter of 0.76, and a group-level variance of 0.59 ($SE = 0.22$). In the creativity domain for Song 3, the UG again demonstrated minimal bias (Cohen’s $d = -0.074$, $p = 0.694$), with AI and human pieces rated equivalently. The IG results mirrored this pattern (Cohen’s $d = -0.018$, $p = 0.923$), confirming that knowledge of the source did not materially influence perceived creativity for this particular excerpt. Overall, creativity ratings reveal a more complex pattern, with human-composed music generally rated higher, though the magnitude of the effect depends on song-specific and item-specific influences as well as participants’ knowledge of the music’s origin. Figure 3 depicts the mean creativity ratings (\pm 95% CI) for Songs 1–4, highlighting the more nuanced, song-specific pattern of AI vs. human biases across the Uninformed and Informed Groups.

3.4 Comparative synthesis and model quality

Across all domains, the mixed linear models converged satisfactorily, with the random effect of participant contributing significantly to the variance in ratings. Log-likelihood and scale parameter values were within acceptable ranges (approximately 0.63 to 1.02 for the scale parameter), and the group-level variances indicate that a substantial proportion of the variability is attributable to individual differences. In summary, authenticity ratings generally favored human-composed music—with effect sizes ranging from moderate (approximately 0.43 in Song 1) to strong (up to 1.42 in Song 2). In contrast, source effects on emotionality were more modest, suggesting that emotional responses are less strongly differentiated. Creativity ratings were more nuanced; while human-composed pieces were frequently preferred (especially in Song 2), the effects varied and were moderated by specific song and item characteristics as well as by participants’ information status (UG vs. IG). Furthermore, the pairwise t-tests confirm that the evaluative bias between AI and human music is modulated by whether participants were uninformed (UG) or informed (IG) regarding the music’s origin.

4 Conclusions

In this study, we investigated how AI-generated music (via Suno AI) compares to human-composed music on listener evaluations of authenticity, creativity, and induced emotion, and how these judgments are modulated by explicit information about the source. Across four stylistically distinct songs, AI-generated excerpts were, on average, rated lower than human compositions on all three

dimensions. Authenticity showed the most robust source effects (often moderate-to-large, up to 1.42), with occasional reversals. Creativity effects were more song-specific (with the largest bias in Song 2), and induced emotions exhibited the weakest and most variable differences.

Informing listeners about the presence of AI did not temper the evaluative gap. Throughout, when we refer to a “gap,” we mean the absolute difference between group means ($|Human - AI|$). Averaged across the four songs, absolute Human–AI differences were larger in the Informed Group than in the Uninformed Group (authenticity, emotionality, and creativity). In this generic-disclosure setting (no per-clip labels), transparency did not mitigate negative expectancy biases and may even amplify them. This has practical implications for platforms and creators aiming to introduce AI-assisted works while maintaining listener engagement and trust.

The null effects observed for induced emotions and creativity in Song 3—especially within the Informed Group (IG)—indicate that AI- and human-composed excerpts were rated virtually identically. This stands in contrast to the pronounced source differences seen in the other songs and suggests that certain genres or compositional structures may mitigate listener bias. Future work should explore how genre-specific characteristics and song structure interact with perceived authorship to shape evaluative judgments.

Overall, our findings highlight a persistent “creative perception gap” in which AI compositions are penalized relative to human works, but also reveal conditions under which this gap can narrow. This underscores the importance of including diverse musical styles and explicit source-information manipulations when assessing AI creativity.

4.1 Limitations

Despite its contributions, this study has several limitations. First, our modest sample size ($N = 31$) and reliance on only four creative prompts may limit the generalizability of our findings across different listener populations and musical genres. Second, we evaluated a single commercial model (Suno AI); results may differ for alternative architectures or training data. Third, we used self-report Likert scales, which capture only conscious judgments and may overlook implicit or physiological responses. Fourth, the online format introduced uncontrolled variability in playback devices and listening environments, potentially influencing ratings. Fifth, our authenticity and creativity scales were author-constructed based on existing literature but lack formal psychometric validation. Sixth, our between-subjects information manipulation cannot fully disentangle expectancy effects from individual skepticism toward AI; future studies might employ within-subjects designs or more granular belief measures. Seventh, stimulus heterogeneity was constrained: we did not sample multiple renditions per prompt nor equate audio-quality artifacts across AI and human outputs—Suno AI occasionally produces phasing or compression artifacts that could bias listener preferences. Moreover, because all human compositions were produced by a single professional composer, our findings may not generalize to works by other creators or production styles. Future studies should involve multiple human composers to assess whether listener biases toward AI versus human music vary as a function of individual artistic voice. Eighth, we did not measure participants’ personal music preferences, which are known to shape perceptions of authenticity, creativity, and emotional impact; including genre or artist preference as a covariate would strengthen future work. Finally, this study offers only a temporal snapshot as generative music systems evolve rapidly; it will be important to reassess whether these evaluative biases persist or diminish and to establish best practices for integrating AI tools without compromising listener engagement.

4.2 Future Directions

Future research should adopt within-subject label manipulations—presenting participants with both labeled and unlabeled versions of the same musical excerpts—to quantify expectancy effects more precisely, as recommended by Déguernel and Sturm (2023). It will also be important to expand the stimulus set to include multiple state-of-the-art AI models alongside compositions from several different human creators, allowing us to disentangle the roles of model architecture and individual artistic voice in shaping listener judgments. At the same time, the authenticity and creativity scales developed here would benefit from formal psychometric validation—following best practices in scale development—to ensure their reliability and construct validity across a broader range of musical genres and listening contexts. Investigating specific musical features—such as timbre, rhythmic

complexity, and melodic contour—that might bridge the perception gap could reveal the compositional characteristics most resistant to bias (cf. Liao (2024) and Sarmiento et al. (2024)). Finally, integrating implicit measures—such as physiological arousal or reaction-time paradigms—alongside traditional self-report ratings would offer a more comprehensive view of both conscious and unconscious aspects of listener engagement with AI- versus human-composed music.

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